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Article

Implementation of Differentiated Instruction and Available Resource Materials in Special Education in Identified Schools of Cebu City Division

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Abstract: This study investigates the extent to which teachers implement differentiated instruction (DI) for learners with special educational needs (LSENs) across four dimensions: content, process, product, and learning environment. The data reveals a generally high level of implementation, particularly in the use of manipulatives, hands-on activities, and diverse presentation formats. Key resources such as manipulatives, printers, and sensory materials are frequently utilized, underscoring their importance in supporting DI strategies. A correlation analysis demonstrates a weak positive relationship between the availability of resource materials and the extent of DI implementation ($r = 0.489$, $p = 0.000$), highlighting the significance of resource availability in enhancing DI effectiveness. The findings suggest that adequate resources are crucial for the successful implementation of differentiated instruction, ultimately improving educational outcomes for LSENs.

Keywords: Differentiated instruction, resource materials, special education, learning environment

Introduction

Education is a fundamental right and a powerful tool for personal and societal development. Mason-Williams et al. (2020) emphasized that the importance of education extends to all individuals, including those with special needs. Special Education is designed to cater to the unique needs of learners with disabilities, ensuring they receive an equitable and quality education (Forlin & Chambers, 2020). According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), inclusive education is essential for achieving social justice and equality (UNESCO, 2019). SpEd programs aim to

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address diverse learning needs, fostering an inclusive environment where every student can thrive.

Differentiated instruction is a pedagogical approach that addresses the diverse learning needs of students, particularly those in Special Education. This method involves tailoring teaching strategies, content, and assessments to meet the varying abilities and interests of learners (Bernacki et al., 2021). Research indicates that differentiated instruction is crucial in Special Education as it enhances student engagement and learning outcomes (Tomlinson, 2020). Recognizing and addressing individual differences, teachers can provide more effective and meaningful learning experiences for students with special educational needs (SEN) (Coates et al., 2020).

The importance of differentiated instruction in Special Education cannot be overstated (Demetriou, 2022). It ensures that all students, regardless of their abilities, have access to a curriculum that meets their needs. Additionally, the availability of resource materials plays a critical role in supporting differentiated instruction. Quality resources enable teachers to implement varied instructional strategies and create adaptive learning environments (Friend & Bursuck, 2021). Therefore, integrating differentiated instruction with appropriate resources is essential for the success of SPED programs.

Utilizing available resources in teaching Special Education is vital for effective instruction. Resources such as adaptive technology, specialized curriculum materials, and assistive devices help create an inclusive learning environment (Viner et al., 2020). These resources support differentiated instruction by providing alternative ways for students to access and engage with the content (Smith et al., 2022). Moreover, professional development for teachers on using these resources can enhance their instructional practices and improve student outcomes. Moreover, the integration of available resources in Special Education is critical for fostering effective instruction and achieving positive educational outcomes (Billingsley et al., 2020). Adaptive technology, such as speech-to-text software and interactive whiteboards, allows students with various disabilities to participate actively in the learning process (Edyburn, 2020). Specialized curriculum materials tailored to individual learning needs, like visual aids and tactile resources, enhance comprehension and engagement. Assistive devices, including hearing aids and mobility tools, support physical and sensory needs, promoting independence and accessibility in the classroom (Johnston et al., 2021). Furthermore, continuous professional development for educators on utilizing these resources is essential. Training equips teachers with the necessary skills to effectively integrate technology and specialized materials into their teaching practices, thereby improving instructional quality and student performance (Müller & Goldenberg, 2019). Leveraging these resources, educators can create a more inclusive and supportive educational

environment, addressing the diverse needs of students with disabilities and facilitating their academic and social development.

Despite the recognized importance of differentiated instruction and resource utilization, there are still gaps in research. One key area of inquiry is the extent to which respondents implement differentiated instruction for learners with special educational needs (LSEs) concerning content, process, product, and learning environment. Another significant gap is identifying the available resources utilized by SPED teachers in implementing differentiation strategies. Addressing these gaps is crucial for improving instructional practices and resource allocation in SpEd programs.

The direction of this research focuses on SPED public-school teachers in Cebu City, Philippines. This study aims to investigate the implementation of differentiated instruction and the availability of resource materials in SPED settings. By understanding the current practices and challenges faced by SPED teachers, the research seeks to provide insights that can inform policy and practice, ultimately enhancing the quality of education for students with special needs in Cebu City.

Methodology

This research utilized a descriptive correlational research design to investigate the implementation of Differentiated Instruction in the Special Education schools of Cebu City Public Schools. Descriptive correlational research, as described by Salaria (2012), involves inquiry, interpretation, and knowledge development by examining individuals' and groups' beliefs and social actions. Oshima and Hogue (2013) emphasize that this design entails specific research procedures, while Hood (2011) highlights the critical decisions made during study planning. Data were collected using an adapted research instrument aligned with the study's objectives, primarily through questionnaires. The gathered data were organized, sorted, tallied, treated, and analyzed to answer the research questions. The study targeted Special Education public school teachers in Cebu City, encompassing three schools in the Northern District and eight in the Southern District. Respondents, who were selected through random sampling to ensure a minimum of 50 samples for reliability, included SpEd teachers involved in teaching learners with special educational needs (LSEs) and implementing Differentiated Instruction daily. To assess the extent of implementation, a 4-point Likert scale with parametric scaling (highly implemented, implemented, less implemented, and not implemented) was used.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Age and Gender

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
50-59	5	10.00	1	2.00	6	12.00
40-49	12	24.00	3	6.00	15	30.00
30-39	19	38.00	2	4.00	21	42.00
20-29	8	16.00	0	0.00	8	16.00
Total	44	88.00	6	12.00	50	100.00

The data in Table 1 provides an overview of the age and gender distribution of teachers. Among the 50 teachers surveyed, the majority are female, comprising 88% of the total. When broken down by age group, it is evident that the largest age cohort among female teachers is 30-39 years, with 19 teachers representing 38% of the total sample. In contrast, only 2 male teachers fall within this age group, making up 4% of the total. The 40-49 age group has the second-highest representation among females, with 12 teachers accounting for 24% of the total, while males in this age range account for 6%, represented by 3 teachers. The youngest age group, 20-29 years, consists solely of 8 female teachers, constituting 16% of the total. The oldest age group, 50-59 years, has 5 female teachers (10%) and 1 male teacher (2%), summing up to 12% of the total. Overall, the distribution highlights a significant gender imbalance, with female teachers predominantly outnumbering their male counterparts across all age groups.

Table 2. Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	f	%
Doctorate Degree	4	8.00
With Doctorate Units	3	6.00
Master's Graduate	13	26.00
With Master's Units	23	46.00
Bachelor's Degree	7	14.00
Total	50	100.00

The data in Table 2 outlines the highest educational attainment levels of a group of 50 teachers. The majority of the teachers, 46%, have earned units towards a Master's degree, indicating that nearly half of the teachers are pursuing advanced education beyond a Bachelor's degree. Additionally, 26% of the teachers have completed their Master's degrees, further emphasizing the high level of educational attainment among the group. A smaller proportion, 14%, hold a Bachelor's degree as their highest qualification. Doctorate degree holders constitute 8% of the sample, while those with some doctorate units but not yet a completed doctorate degree make up 6%. This distribution showcases

a commitment to advanced education, with a significant portion of the teachers holding or working towards graduate-level qualifications.

Table 3. Number of Years in Teaching SPED

Number of Years	f	%
15 and above	15	30.00
10-14	5	10.00
5-9	18	36.00
4 and below	12	24.00
Total	50	100.00

The data in Table 3 presents the distribution of teachers based on their number of years in teaching Special Education (SPED). Among the 50 teachers surveyed, the largest group consists of those with 5-9 years of experience, representing 36% of the total. This is followed by teachers with 15 or more years of experience, accounting for 30%. Teachers with 4 or fewer years of experience make up 24% of the sample, while those with 10-14 years of experience constitute the smallest group at 10%. Overall, the distribution indicates a diverse range of experience levels among the SPED teachers, with a significant number having substantial experience of five years or more in the field.

Table 4. Number of Hours of Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended by the Respondents

Number of Hours	f	%
30 and above	12	24.00
20-29	9	18.00
10-19	15	30.00
9 and below	14	28.00
Total	50	100.00

The data in Table 4 illustrates the number of hours of relevant trainings and seminars attended by the respondents. Out of the 50 respondents, the majority (30%) have attended between 10-19 hours of relevant training and seminars. This is followed by 28% who have attended 9 hours or fewer. A significant portion, 24%, have attended 30 hours or more, indicating a substantial commitment to professional development among this group. Finally, 18% of the respondents have participated in 20-29 hours of training and seminars. Overall, the distribution shows a wide range of training and seminar attendance, with a notable number of respondents investing considerable time in professional development activities.

The data in Table 5 provides an overview of the types of disabilities handled by the respondents, ranked by frequency. Intellectual Disability is the most commonly handled disability, with 29 respondents indicating experience in this area, ranking it first. Autism follows closely with 24 respondents, making it the second most frequently managed disability.

Table 5. Type of Disabilities Handled by the Respondents

Type of Disabilities	f	Rank
Intellectual Disability	29	1
Autism	24	2
Multiple Disabilities	15	3
Specific Learning Disability	6	4
Hearing Impairment	5	5
Other Health Impairment	4	6
Deafness	3	8
Emotional Disturbance	3	8
Speech Language Impairment	3	8
Orthopedic Impairment	1	10.5
Visual Impairment	1	10.5

*multiple response

Multiple Disabilities are handled by 15 respondents, placing it third in rank. Specific Learning Disability, handled by 6 respondents, ranks fourth. Hearing Impairment is managed by 5 respondents, ranking fifth. Other Health Impairment is handled by 4 respondents, ranking sixth. Deafness, Emotional Disturbance, and Speech Language Impairment are each managed by 3 respondents, tying them at eighth rank. Orthopedic Impairment and Visual Impairment are the least commonly handled disabilities, each managed by only 1 respondent, tying them at tenth rank. The data highlights that Intellectual Disability and Autism are the most prevalent disabilities managed by the respondents, while fewer respondents handle more specialized impairments like Orthopedic and Visual Impairments.

Table 6. Extent to which the Respondents Implement Differentiated Instruction for LSENs in terms of its Content

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	I provide varying reading materials that are aligned to the developmental level of the student with Specific Learning Disabilities.	3.26	0.78	Highly Implemented
2	Reorganizing content by describing similarities and categorizing accordingly.	3.14	0.88	Implemented
3	Content is aligned to application of skills	3.24	0.74	Implemented
4	Lessons are varied according to student interest.	3.32	0.77	Highly Implemented
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.24		Implemented
	Aggregate Standard Deviation		0.79	

The data in Table 6 examines the extent to which teachers implement differentiated instruction for learners with special educational needs (LSENs) in terms of content. Four key indicators were assessed, each showing varying degrees of implementation. The highest-rated indicator, with a weighted mean (WM) of 3.32 and a standard deviation

(SD) of 0.77, is the variation of lessons according to student interest, which is classified as "Highly Implemented." Similarly, providing varying reading materials aligned to the developmental levels of students with specific learning disabilities also received a "Highly Implemented" rating, with a WM of 3.26 and an SD of 0.78. Other indicators, such as aligning content to the application of skills and reorganizing content by describing similarities and categorizing, have WMs of 3.24 and 3.14 respectively, both falling under the "Implemented" category. The overall aggregate weighted mean is 3.24, with an aggregate standard deviation of 0.79, indicating that, on average, differentiated instruction in terms of content is generally implemented, with some areas being more emphasized, particularly those related to student interest and developmental alignment.

Table 7. Extent to which the Respondents Implement Differentiated Instruction for LSENs in terms of its Process

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Provision of varying supports by how much the student needs	3.00	0.88	Implemented
2	Utilization of graphic organizers, concept maps or charts that provide visual cues in the classroom.	3.06	0.79	Implemented
3	Incorporating tiered activities to incorporate the same skills.	2.96	0.75	Implemented
4	Establishing centers within the classroom to allow further learning of current lessons.	2.82	0.94	Implemented
5	Using student specific task sheets that are individualized according to the category of Specific Learning Disability.	3.14	0.86	Implemented
6	Utilization of manipulative and hands-on activities.	3.32	0.79	Highly Implemented
7	Presenting learning through various means: audio/visual, varying text size and color contrast	3.20	0.78	Implemented
8	Varying time and support for specific tasks.	3.00	0.76	Implemented
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.06		Implemented
	Aggregate Standard Deviation		0.82	

The data in Table 7 assesses the extent to which teachers implement differentiated instruction for learners with special educational needs (LSENs) in terms of their teaching process. The highest level of implementation is observed in the utilization of manipulative and hands-on activities, with a WM of 3.32 and an SD of 0.79, earning a "Highly Implemented" rating. Other indicators, while not rated as highly, are consistently "Implemented." These include the use of student-specific task sheets tailored to the category of specific learning disability (WM 3.14, SD 0.86), presenting learning through various means such as audio/visual aids, varying text size, and color contrast (WM 3.20, SD 0.78), and utilization of graphic organizers, concept maps, or charts for visual cues (WM 3.06, SD 0.79). Further indicators

such as providing varying supports based on student needs (WM 3.00, SD 0.88), incorporating tiered activities to develop the same skills (WM 2.96, SD 0.75), establishing centers within the classroom for further learning of current lessons (WM 2.82, SD 0.94), and varying time and support for specific tasks (WM 3.00, SD 0.76) are also marked as "Implemented." The aggregate weighted mean for these indicators is 3.06, with an aggregate standard deviation of 0.82, indicating an overall consistent implementation of differentiated instructional processes among teachers, with particular emphasis on hands-on and visually supported activities. This suggests a strong commitment to adapting teaching methods to meet diverse learning needs.

Table 8. Extent to which the Respondents Implement Differentiated Instruction for LSEs in terms of its Product

S/ N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Giving alternatives in the learning environment	2.80	0.97	Implemented
2	Encouraging creation of individual products that contain "aspects" of the assignment.	2.90	0.86	Implemented
3	Providing expectations that are attainable	3.20	0.81	Implemented
4	Establishing centers within the classroom to allow further learning of current lessons.	2.74	0.99	Implemented
5	Using student specific task sheets that are individualized according to the category of Specific Learning Disability.	3.12	0.87	Implemented
6	Utilization of manipulative and hands-on activities.	3.28	0.78	Highly Implemented
7	Presenting learning through various means: audio/visual, varying text size and color contrast	3.14	0.88	Implemented
8	Varying time and support for specific tasks that allow for varying degree of difficulty	3.04	0.75	Implemented
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.03		Implemented
	Aggregate Standard Deviation		0.86	

The data in Table 8 evaluates the extent to which teachers implement differentiated instruction for learners with special educational needs (LSEs) in terms of the product of learning activities.. The highest level of implementation is found in the utilization of manipulative and hands-on activities, with a WM of 3.28 and an SD of 0.78, rated as "Highly Implemented." Other indicators generally fall into the "Implemented" category. These include providing expectations that are attainable (WM 3.20, SD 0.81), presenting learning through various means such as audio/visual aids, varying text size, and color contrast (WM 3.14, SD 0.88), and using student-specific task sheets individualized according to the category of specific learning disability (WM 3.12, SD 0.87). Encouraging the creation of individual products containing aspects of the assignment (WM 2.90, SD 0.86), giving alternatives in the learning environment (WM 2.80, SD 0.97), and establishing centers within the classroom for further learning of current lessons (WM 2.74, SD 0.99) are all noted as "Implemented," though with

lower mean scores. Additionally, varying time and support for specific tasks to allow for varying degrees of difficulty is also "Implemented" with a WM of 3.04 and an SD of 0.75. The aggregate weighted mean for these indicators is 3.03, with an aggregate standard deviation of 0.86, indicating a consistent level of implementation of differentiated instruction in terms of product across the board. The data suggests that while there is a general application of differentiated instructional strategies, hands-on and manipulative activities are the most effectively and frequently implemented methods.

Table 9. Extent to which the Respondents Implement Differentiated Instruction for LSENs in terms of its Learning Environment

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	Giving consideration as to where students give their best thinking.	2.68	1.00	Implemented
2	Considerations as to where students learn best	2.78	1.09	Implemented
3	Including structured guidelines where students are more comfortable in familiar settings.	3.18	0.77	Implemented
4	Creating a positive learning environment by incorporating materials that encourage student collaboration.	3.16	0.91	Implemented
5	Establishing routines that are so consistent that they almost become tangible.	3.16	0.84	Implemented
	Aggregate Weighted Mean	3.00		Implemented
	Aggregate Standard Deviation		0.92	

The data in Table 9 evaluates the extent to which teachers implement differentiated instruction for learners with special educational needs (LSENs) in terms of the learning environment. The highest levels of implementation are seen in the inclusion of structured guidelines where students are more comfortable in familiar settings (WM 3.18, SD 0.77), creating a positive learning environment by incorporating materials that encourage student collaboration (WM 3.16, SD 0.91), and establishing consistent routines (WM 3.16, SD 0.84). All three indicators are rated as "Implemented." Other indicators, such as giving consideration to where students learn best (WM 2.78, SD 1.09) and where they give their best thinking (WM 2.68, SD 1.00), are also "Implemented," although they have slightly lower mean scores and higher standard deviations, indicating more variability in implementation. The aggregate weighted mean for these indicators is 3.00, with an aggregate standard deviation of 0.92, suggesting that overall, the implementation of differentiated instruction in terms of the learning environment is consistent but with room for improvement. The data indicates that while structured guidelines and positive, collaborative environments are well-established, there is greater variability and slightly lower implementation in considerations of optimal learning and thinking environments for students.

Table 10 Available Resources Utilized by the Respondents in Differentiated Instruction

Available Resources	f	Rank
Manipulatives	44	1
Printer	39	2
Cleaning Equipment	38	3
Sensory Materials	36	4
Activities of Daily Living Charts/Schedules	34	5
Smart TV/Interactive Board	27	6
Audio/Speakers/Headphones	26	7
Kitchen/Cooking equipment's	17	8
LCD Projector	16	9
Timers	11	10
Round Table	9	11
Braille/Zoomtech	8	12
Horseshoe Table	6	13
Kidney Table	3	14

*multiple response

The data in Table 10 reveals the variety of resources used by respondents in differentiated instruction for learners with special educational needs (LSENs). The most frequently utilized resource is manipulatives, employed by 44 respondents. Other commonly used resources include printers (39 respondents), cleaning equipment (38 respondents), sensory materials (36 respondents), and activities of daily living charts/schedules (34 respondents). Additionally, smart TVs or interactive boards (27 respondents) and audio equipment like speakers and headphones (26 respondents) are also notable. Less frequently utilized resources include kitchen and cooking equipment (17 respondents), LCD projectors (16 respondents), timers (11 respondents), round tables (9 respondents), Braille/Zoomtech (8 respondents), horseshoe tables (6 respondents), and kidney tables (3 respondents). Overall, the data underscores a significant emphasis on hands-on learning tools and a wide range of other resources to support differentiated instruction.

Table 11. Test of Relationship between the extent of implementation of DI and available of resource materials utilized by the respondents

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p - value	Decision	Remarks
Implementation of DI and Available Resources	0.489*	Weak Positive	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

*significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed)

The data in Table 11 examines the relationship between the extent of implementation of differentiated instruction (DI) and the availability of resource materials utilized by the respondents. The correlation analysis yields an r-value of 0.489, indicating a weak positive correlation between the two variables. This suggests that as the availability of

resource materials increases, there is a slight but positive increase in the extent of DI implementation. The p-value is 0.000, which is below the significance threshold of 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0). This result is significant, indicating that the availability of resources is statistically associated with the extent to which differentiated instruction is implemented.

Conclusion

The collected data offers a comprehensive view of how differentiated instruction (DI) is implemented for learners with special educational needs (LSENs) across various dimensions of content, process, product, and learning environment by the respondents. The analysis indicates that overall, the respondents are effectively implementing DI, particularly in areas like utilizing manipulatives and hands-on activities, presenting content in diverse formats, and providing structured and supportive learning environments. The availability of resources such as manipulatives, printers, and sensory materials is high, suggesting that these tools play a critical role in supporting DI strategies. The correlation analysis shows a weak positive relationship (r-value of 0.489) between the extent of DI implementation and the availability of resource materials, with a significant p-value of 0.000, indicating that better availability of resources positively influences the extent of DI implementation. This emphasizes the importance of ensuring sufficient resources to enhance the effectiveness of differentiated instruction for LSENs.

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